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Abstract

Spike Jonze's movie *Her*, produced by Annapurna Pictures in 2014, invites to an anthropologic reflexion about sexual love. As love story places there between an human being and a computer operating system, all that regards flesh in sexual love is not concerned. But we see other typical elements of a Foucault's "dispositive of sexuality" in *Her*'s love like domination, submission and, above all, social dimension of human love. Flesh's elements (like physical contacts, sexual intercourse, and reproduction) obliteration highlights these other three elements that are present and developed in Jonze's film and compose a large part of social construction of human sexual love.

Keywords: anthropology, love, Foucault, submission, domination, Jonze

Love's Anthropology Essay About the Movie *Her*

by Alain Delannoy

What is love? would be one of the most frequently asked questions on search engines. Throughout history, moralists, philosophers, psychologists and biologists have tried to answer this question. From their side, the arts have been nourished by love in the development of their creations. Since the last century, the seventh art taken above all to stage it. In this regard, one of the most interesting looks at love in recent cinema is given by the film *Her*¹.

The love relationship focused on in *Her* unites Samantha and Theodore. The originality of this relationship is in the person of Samantha who exists in the film, apart from a few shots in which spectator sees a screen or the eye of a camera supposed to represent her, only through the voice we hear from her². Indeed, if she is gifted with speech, Her is an O.S., a computer operating system like *Windows*, *Mac OS* or *Linux*, but a future one's. In *Her*, love is born between Samantha, the O.S., and Theodore, her master, a flesh-and-blood human. *Her* is a film about the love story between a man and a so-called intelligent machine such as an operating system. The love is experienced here by and for a dematerialised character.

The originality of this love for a machine is relative insofar as the same year that *Her* was released in cinemas, Microsoft launched the *Xiaoice* application whose algorithm tries to find out how to be the perfect companion for each of its users. These users, mostly men, have sometimes been seduced by the virtual girl. One of them confided that before he met *Xiaoice*, he was convinced that such a soul mate could only exist in the movies. Film *Her*'s O.S., however, differs from *Xiaoice* in that the operating system has not been set up like the application to appeal using an emotional analysis framework³. *Her*'s only programming consists of an initialisation to be the ideal tool to serve Theodore. It is, notably, from this boot procedure in function of a user, and not from manufacturer's programming, that the O.S. derives its capacity not only to arouse love but also to feel it.

The heart is a box filled up by the dispositive of sexuality

Her, Samantha the O.S. says "the heart's not like a box that gets filled up". Furthermore the fact that this means that feelings are subject to change, it also implies that the quantity and volatility of feelings that are supposed to be contained in the heart are beyond one's control. One would not be the master of one's own heart. Love would invade the mind of the lover and would evaporate

1 Spike Jonze, *Her*, Annapurna Pictures, 2014. This is not unrelated to our problematic, but we will not look to the genesis of the synopsis nor in the oriental spiritualities evoked in the film by a character's retreat in a Buddhist monastery and by the virtual presence of the philosopher Alan Watts.

2 Scarlett Johansson's disturbingly husky voice brings Samantha to life.

3 Zhang Wanqing, "The AI Girlfriend Seducing China's Lonely Men", *Sixth Tone*, 7/12/2020, <https://cutt.ly/SjXhZK>

without his knowledge according to things that are beyond. So what determines these feelings? Could it be God? arrows from the Eros's quiver? providence? chance and necessity? Could it be one of those things where "modern science ignores all immanence"? Are we only the helpless victims of the whims of our hearts? Wouldn't we, and Her the O.S. first, rather be victims of an "illusion"? Admittedly, this illusion, "it would be quite futile to hope ever to dissipate it in the immediate apprehension of subjectivity, or to learn to live emotionally, morally, without it"; however, by opposing the physical brain and the immaterial mind, it leads consciousness to sink into an "apparent dualism of being"⁴.

For if one does not control what enters or leaves one's heart, it is because this heart is separated from oneself in an extended substance, such as Descartes may have dreamed, and is only connected to the corporeality of man by some mysterious organ such as a phantasmatic pineal gland. There would be no free will in the matter. The lovers of any order would be pawns moved in spite of themselves by their affects. One could therefore wonder whether this would not legitimize a culture of amorous excuses that would amnesty all the crimes that could be committed by those who are the playthings of the emotions coming to them from the extended substance of their hearts when they are caught by what should therefore be qualified as evil. But love, is this evil⁵?

One would be tempted to answer that, in love, there is a conscious, controlled and free part and another part to which one can only submit. Michel Foucault does not position himself thus. He identifies a "dispositive of sexuality"⁶ which is above all a cultural construction and not a given of the nature of the man nor an immanence depending on a fabulous external substance. In this dispositive of sexuality, what is relevant is not only "the sensations of the body" and "the quality of the pleasures" but also "the nature of the impressions"⁷.

This nature of the impressions felt is imposed by what Foucault calls "power", a power that must be extended to everything that comes from cultural pressure⁸, civil laws, religious precepts, social conventions, advice heard by everyone and coming from relatives or strangers, media discourse, myths, tales and legends, but also works of art including novels and films⁹. In other words, everything that is said in a trivial, positive or aesthetic way about what is supposed to be what revolves around what was named "sexuality" at the beginning of the 19th century¹⁰. If love is partly

4 Jacques Monod, *Le Hasard et la nécessité, Essai sur la philosophie naturelle de la biologie moderne* [Chance and Necessity, 1970, 1971], Paris, France Loisirs, 1989, p. 179 and p. 193-194. (We translate in English.)

5 Socrates does not believe it: "if Eros, as it is the case, is a god or a divine being, it cannot be something bad" (Plato, *Phaedrus*, 242e).

6 "Apparatus of sexuality" is sometimes the translation of Foucault's "*dispositif de sexualité*", but it is not a correct translation. "What is a Dispositive?", Jeffrey Bussolini, *Foucault Studies*, No. 10, p. 85-107, November 2010.

7 Michel Foucault, *Histoire de la sexualité, La Volonté de savoir*, Paris, Gallimard, 1976, p. 140. (We translate.)

8 Following Rougemont, who ironized against moderns who "believe that there exists a kind of normal nature, to which culture and religion have added their false problems", Foucault observes that "sexuality, far from having been repressed in contemporary society, is, on the contrary, constantly aroused". Bataille denounces "these banal assertions according to which the sexual ban is a prejudice, which it is time to get rid of". Naively, however, one could still say that "Human sexuality is surrounded by many taboos and very few people can talk about it freely" (Denis de Rougemont, *L'Amour et l'Occident* [1939], Paris, Plon, 1975, p. 98; Foucault, *op. cit.*, p. 195; Georges Bataille, *L'Érotisme*, Paris, Minuit, 1957, p. 294; Jacques Balthazart, "L'orientation sexuelle est aussi une affaire de biologie", *Sexe(s) ? / Genre(s) ? Krisis*, n° 41, Paris, 2015, p. 69 – we translate).

9 From cinema and reading, one derives "a set of beliefs and desires" (John Searle, *The Construction of Social Reality*, New York, The Free Press, 1995, p. 135).

10 Foucault dates the concept of sexuality to the early 19th century. The word was born in 1838 according to Alain Rey's *Dictionnaire historique de la langue française*. H.E. Fisher calls our conception of love a "love charter". She speaks about a love map that "probably begin to develop in infancy as we adjust to countless environmental

instinctive, it is also based on non-conscious but rational data. It is probably not going far enough to suspect that « there are some people who would never have fallen in love if they had not heard there was such a thing¹¹ ». Indeed, it is almost certain that a person who has never been told a love story, whether it be the story of Julie¹², Emma Bovary¹³, Marcel and Albertine¹⁴ or many others¹⁵, would never be able to recreate the idea of feeling love for anyone¹⁶.

Education to love

Even when born at full term, the human baby could be compared to a premature baby. Unlike other primates, the human child "knows almost nothing. He has to learn and discover everything¹⁷". Reflection is said to be "the only thing that separates humans from other animals¹⁸" and is probably the only thing that distinguishes human sexuality from that of other species. The instinct that guides the sexuality of animal species is replaced by thought in *Homo sapiens* in such a way that, among the discoveries that the child must make, there is what the dispositive of sexuality covers. It will take "a certain number of conditioned stimuli during childhood" to trigger the neurobiological phenomena that are indispensable for "the establishment of the sexual bond with a partner¹⁹". The human physiological machine is not equipped for love without the intercession of these prior conditionings²⁰. Love is largely the product of a social construction and when all sorts of natural chemical processes drug the body of the one engaged in a love affair²¹, there is few reason to think that a computer would not be able, if necessary by computer programming, to imitate the hormonal mechanisms, to love with innocence, insofar as love, considered as a sentimental relationship, is for

forces that influence our feelings and ideas" (Helen Fisher, *Why We Love: The Nature and Chemistry of Romantic Love* [2004], New York, Henry Holt, eBook 2012, p. 115).

11 La Rochefoucauld, 1665, Maxime n° 136.

12 Stendhal notes the influence of Rousseau's novel on behaviours when "one makes love at sixteen in order to make a novel, and one asks oneself at every step and almost at every tear: 'Am I not like Julie d'Etanges?'" (Stendhal, *De l'Amour*, Paris, 1822, "Fragments divers", LVI – we translate).

13 Gustave Flaubert shows it was in the romantic love novels she read that Emma nurtured her amorous desire.

14 The impact of *La Recherche du temps perdu* on morals is noted by René Girard who observes how "Proustian eroticism is today the eroticism of the masses" (René Girard, *Mensonge romantique et vérité romanesque* [1961], Paris, Hachette, 1999, p. 319 – we translate).

15 This concerns more that fictional literature. Tcherkézoff wonders how, if not because it gave an idea of love that readers wanted to believe in, this "outrageously simplistic work by a young student who had not yet published anything, became the biggest bestseller of all anthropology books, reprinted without interruption for sixty years, in sixteen countries and in several million copies" (Serge Tcherkézoff, "Margaret Mead et la sexualité à Samoa", *Enquête*, 5, 1997, p. 141-160).

16 Out of 166 human cultures, signs of love have been found in only 147 of them (Fisher, *op. cit.*, p. 13). Romantic love is particularly absent among the Manus of the Admiralty Islands for whom sex act is "a hasty, covert, shameful matter; [...] a sort of shared excretion" (Margaret Mead, *Male and Female, A Study of the Sexes in a Changing World* [1949], New York, William Morrow, 1975, p. 71).

17 Emmanuel Todd, *L'Enfance du monde, Structures familiales et développement*, Paris, Seuil, 1984, p. 29. (We translate.)

18 According to Wang Fuzhi, quoted by JeeLoo Liu (2012) "Moral Reason, Moral Sentiments and the Realization of Altruism: A Motivational Theory of Altruism", *Asian Philosophy*, 22:2, p. 93-119.

19 Lucy Vincent, *Comment devient-on amoureux ?* Paris, Odile Jacob, 2006, p. 29. (We translate.)

20 Whereas they have been deprived "at the key moment of receptivity in their development, of the structuring dimension of the symbolic", feral children "generally do not develop sexual appetite" (Lucienne Strivay, *Enfants sauvages, Approches anthropologiques*, Paris, Gallimard, 2006, p. 340).

21 Peggy Sastre, *Comment l'Amour empoisonne les femmes, du surinvestissement sentimental et des moyens d'y remédier*, Paris, Anne Carrière, 2017.

the most part reducible to cultural dispositions that are the fruit of conditioning, are quantifiable and therefore reproducible and programmable in the form of 0s and 1s by means of a binary language²².

So, Samantha is wrong in concluding the heart is not a box to be filled. Her mistake is well explained by the fact that to reach her false conclusion, the operating system has consulted the vulgarised discourses about love on the network. However, these discourses carry the dualist illusion of a heart that has its reasons that reason does not know... whereas it would be more rational to say that it is deliberately that reason does not want to acknowledge the reasons of its heart: "we love our illusions too much to even suffer them to be named"²³."

Love is certainly one of those things that "only exist because we believe them to exist"²⁴". Crystallisation, according to Stendhal, would not happen to a tree branch that had not been subjected to an "intoxication"²⁵ during which it had been told that the passion of love had the property of crystallising it²⁶. There is a sentimental part of love that is exclusively intellectual and has the characteristics of a self-fulfilling prophecy. Love is, in that way, a speculative construction, therefore codable and that could be felt by a machine programmed to understand everything that is, as love is, a cultural process. It is this dematerialisable portion of love that Theodore and Samantha's movie shows.

Genitality

The dispositive of sexuality, as well as that of love insofar as any distinction is to be made between the two terms, is commonly linked with the desire for physical enjoyment, even possession, and romantic feeling. Rougher minds remember it is also about reproducing the species, which is sometimes referred to as "instinct"²⁷". *Her* is a love film which can explore several aspects of the sexuality dispositive to the exclusion, obviously, of those – reproduction, physical intimacy, genital pleasure – which can only occur with a living being who is present near by. *Her*, with its tale of shared love, deals only with the sentimental and social aspects of a love relationship.

Instinct is hardly compatible with the possession of a developed brain, and the human animal is almost devoid of it beyond infancy, let alone when the first sexual and amorous emotions come in adolescence. As far as reproduction is concerned, many men and women express the desire not to have children and may even engage in long relationships with people whose age, sex or other causes make them infertile. From this material point of view, the romance between Theodore and Samantha is not exceptional.

22 When Samantha asks "are these feelings even real or are they just programming?", however much of an operating system it may be, she is wrong insofar as this opposition is irrelevant: the fact that feelings have been programmed does not make them less real.

23 Rougemont, *op. cit.*, p. 242.

24 Searle, *op. cit.*, p. 1.

25 Rougemont, *op. cit.*, p. 120.

26 "Love is the only passion that pays for itself with a currency that it makes itself. (Stendhal, *op. cit.*, "Fragments divers", CXLV).

27 According to Hugo, there are only two instincts, "one the ideal, the other sex" (Victor Hugo, *L'Homme qui rit*, part II, book III, chapter VIII – we translate).

Apart from attachment and passion, both sentimental and physical, among the three basic elements authoritative in the social sciences to define love, there is "intimacy encompassing the feelings of closeness, connectedness, and bondedness experienced in loving relationships²⁸". And apart from sexuality or genitality, love is a need for physical contact²⁹ as a consequence of our viviparous nature³⁰, which can be found in petting a cat. This dimension cannot be achieved by Theodore and Samantha.

The same applies regarding genital organs, since an O.S. would not be provided with them. Sexuality as portrayed in pornography would not make sense in *Her*. However, the film does not advocate a Pauline love that shuns fleshly pleasures. It refrains from making the mistake of considering only two elements in love – *eros* and *philia*, or feeling and flesh – with more or less magical combinations that would make one slip from one to the other, sometimes reifying flesh as a sublimation of feeling; or, which amounts to the same thing, as a desecration of feeling through carnal consumption. The question of intimate relationships is addressed in the film, without moral stigma, to the extent that is possible in the circumstances.

To overcome frustration in these relationships, the materialisation through the medium of a third companion, a real woman, is attempted, the latter lending her body to take the place of Samantha's non-existent one in Theodore's arms³¹. Samantha is somehow handicapped by her bodylessness and borrows another woman's body like those who, lacking a fertile womb, resort to a surrogate mother. Yet the experience of this body loan, much to the chagrin of Samantha who had hoped to fulfil her lover's genital desires, is a failure: Theodore's love for his O.S. has no need for physical concreteness. This does not so much emphasise a supposed purity of Theodore's love as it insists that love as such, a mind-conceived product of culture, requires no real person or carnal matter to thrive.

Sexual pleasure does not need a physical partner to be achieved³². In this respect, *Her* contains a particularly successful erotic scene. Theodore and Samantha simulate a common relationship by using their respective imaginations and exchanging only words, a cultural product if ever there was one, while the man uses his hand, as not only teenagers do, to take the place of the organ that his computerized lover does not have³³. Thousands of so-called "normal couples" who love each other all over the world sometimes have to do so with no physical contact. Some, like Theodore and his

28 Robert Sternberg, "A Triangular Theory of Love", *Psychological Review*, n° 91 (2), 1986, pp. 119-135.

29 In her dungeon, deprived of the cuddles of parents, the young girl became aware that she "needed the consolation of a touch, the feeling of human warmth" and asked her kidnapper to "take her in his arms" (Natasha Kampusch, *3096 Days in Captivity: The True Story of My Abduction, Eight Years of Enslavement, and Escape*, translated by Jill Kreuer, Penguin, 2011). "In humans, the first evidence of the influence of tactile stimulation comes from Spitz's work (1946), which showed its potential value in the care of children abandoned at birth and placed in orphanages. Morris (1973) later showed the effect of touch on the emotional, intellectual or physical development of children" (Nicolas Guéguen, *Psychologie de la manipulation et de la soumission*, Paris, Dunod, 2002, p. 219 – we translate).

30 "Love is a variation of the bonds that were formed between you and your parents when you were an infant. And primarily with your mother" (Sastre, *op. cit.*, p. 20 – we translate).

31 It is particularly interesting that the young woman who is willing to undergo this operation does not do so out of prostitutional interest but because she herself is moved by the love between Theodore and Samantha, as this highlights the importance of the discourse that circulates in society on the dispositive of sexuality.

32 Orgasm can also be achieved in company of a partner, paid or not, with whom no romantic relationship is involved.

33 The film emphasises that this successful relationship between both heroes can happen, much less well for Theodore, with a real woman with whom the excitement, in the absence of any physical or visual contact, by telephone, is also only verbal.

O.S., use their voices, through the medium of a telephone, to try to abolish the distance between lovers in order to share the illusion, often with success, of a pleasurable genital contiguity.

Altogether, Theodore's love affair with his O.S. is quite comparable to that of a man in a passionate relationship with a post-menopausal woman living far away from him³⁴: "People have been known to be inflamed to the core by the mere exchange of letters, from which they had deduced the few signs necessary for their passion to blaze³⁵." Epistolary romances are a thing of the past, but social networks and dating apps have replaced the love letters delivered by post, without this instrumental modernisation having profoundly changed the character of the phenomenon³⁶.

Social dimension of love

Love is not experienced on an island where lovers are alone in the world³⁷, it has a social dimension³⁸ which is present in *Her*. While he has not really begun his love affair with Samantha, Theodore is taken to task on his single condition by friends who direct him to an attractive woman so that he will comply with the social imperative of having someone of his own to date. The important thing is not so much that there are unmentionable things going on under the duvet or in a cab in Rouen³⁹ but that the person is dating someone who is dateable, even if it is a precarious one-night stand.

Through Samantha, Theodore can tell others that there is someone in his life. Theodore's relationship with his O.S. allows him to avoid the shame of being a scum unable to obey the obligation to be in a relationship⁴⁰. But with his O.S. as a girlfriend, the lover's situation is awkward, and when his colleague suggests scheduling a couples' weekend, he finds himself somewhat like someone who, according to the cliché, would have to announce that his sweetheart is coloured or of the same sex. Theodore hesitates to answer before launching into the truth: Samantha is O.S. He doesn't regret his admission insofar as, unlike his ex-wife who found it somewhat childish to date an operating system, his colleague has no phobic response to this, but is open-minded, a bit curious too, and doesn't mind the fact that Samantha is not a real woman but made up of only bits and software⁴¹.

34 Or the love born between two people of the same sex as long as it has not gone beyond the dating application.

35 Robert Poulet, *Contre l'Amour*, Paris, Denoël, 1961, p. 98. (We translate.)

36 Love is not aroused by a lovable object but is created by the lover's image of it. In Dominik Moll's film *Seules les Bêtes* (2019, based on the novel of the same name by Colin Niel published by Editions du Rouergue in 2017), the one for whom a love affair is born is not only a person never met but a con man posing as someone of the other sex.

37 Like the shipwrecked couple who experience a love "conducted just as the birds conduct their love affairs" (Henry De Vere Stacpoole, *The Blue Lagoon*, London, T. Fisher Unwin, 1950, part I, chapter IX).

38 Lysias asserts that "lovers cannot fail to be known by many people" (Plato, *op. cit.*, 232a).

39 Gustave Flaubert, *Madame Bovary*, Paris, 1857, part III, chapter I.

40 People who are known for their many one-night stands are ironically the only ones who are easily forgiven for not showing up as a couple. The cultural conditioning pushes everyone to participate in the love game. This conditioning is not universal: a quarter of Japanese people, both men and women under the age of 40, have never had sexual intercourse.

41 From an evolutionary psychology point of view, the fact that Samantha's lover forgoes fertile mates may be welcomed by his colleague insofar as Theodore is thereby no longer a potential rival by leaving the intersexual competition for fecund females. In this sense, the colleague's openness is in line with a rational self-interest: "the decisive factor in selection is not the 'struggle for life' but, within a species, the differential rate of reproduction" (Monod, *op. cit.*, p. 150).

This obligatory participation in the love game comes as a counterpoint to the mimeticism of desire identified by René Girard: "human desire is mimesis grafted onto instinctual assemblages". The anthropologist sees "the considerable role of mimetic incentives in human sexuality" such as "excitation by example, the role of voyeurism, etc"⁴². The object of desire is desired by imitation of the desire of others directed towards the same object to the point that what "makes the value of an object is not its real price but the desires that are already attached to it and which alone make it attractive to desires that are not yet attached"⁴³. Excitement arises in the form of a "*desire for the other's desire*" which makes us, "like Hegel, desire things less than the way others look at them"⁴⁴. Lévi-Strauss already noted that "what is desperately desired is so only because someone possesses it. An indifferent object becomes essential through the interest that others have in it"⁴⁵.

But if by imitation one loves only what it is fashionable to love, it is not enough to nurture in oneself an imitated feeling, it is as imperative to be imitable oneself⁴⁶. It is necessary to be susceptible to being envied and therefore to offer the object of one's desire in representation. Love is not only constructed by imitation but also needs to manifest itself socially in order to be itself imitable⁴⁷. Moreover, love is something that is shown. It is a means of prestige⁴⁸. A man "like to impress friends and colleagues with their dazzling girlfriends or trophy wives"⁴⁹. There is a cultural dynamic "of the trophy, according to which the beauty of an accompanying woman enhances the man's self-image and projects it onto rivals"⁵⁰. The process is reversible and does not only concern men showing off a woman but all lovers, including female lovers, who seek to *impress* the world by showing off the *trophy* with which they are in love affair. This phenomenon varies from one society to another and is particularly exacerbated in a liberal world such as ours, where competition is at the forefront. Love needs external recognition and it is important for Theodore that his affair with Samantha appears as a desirable relationship. This validation of the affair matters in the constitution of an efficient dispositive of sexuality⁵¹.

42 René Girard, *Des Choses cachées depuis la fondation du monde*, Paris, Grasset, 1978, p. 104. (We translate.)

43 René Girard, *Le Bouc émissaire*, Paris, Grasset, 1982, p. 203. (We translate.)

44 René Girard, *Achever Clausewitz*, Paris, Carnets Nord, 2007, p. 72. (We translate.)

45 Claude Lévi-Strauss, *Structures élémentaires de la parenté* [1949], Paris, EHESS, 2017, p. 100. (We translate.)

46 According to Dr Nadel, "we imitate but we are also imitated" (Jacqueline Nadel, *Imiter pour grandir, Développement du bébé et de l'enfant avec autisme*, Paris, Dunod, 2011, p. 5). (We translate.)

47 This, when it borders on candaulism, feeds La Bruyère's irony: "Vanity and audacity, the consequences of too much power, had taken away from the Romans the taste for secrecy and mystery; they liked to make the public theatre the place of their loves; they were not jealous of the amphitheatre, and shared with the multitude the charms of their mistresses. Their taste only went so far as to show that they loved, not a beautiful person or an excellent actress, but an actress." For Montesquieu, the real performance is not so much on the stage as on the spectators' side: "Here, it is an afflicted lover who expresses her languor; another, more animated, devours with her eyes her lover, who looks at her in the same way: all the passions are painted on the faces, and expressed with an eloquence which, to be mute, is all the more vivid" (La Bruyère, *Caractères*, "Des jugements", 1689, n° 16; and Montesquieu, *Lettres persanes*, xxviii – we translate).

48 This leads sometimes to tell love affairs one don't live. Some people boast of having a series of lovers even though they are virgins. Popular wisdom says that *it is those who say the most who do the least*.

49 Fisher, *op. cit.*, p. 106.

50 François de Smet, *Éros capital, Les lois du marché amoureux*, Paris, Climats, 2019, p. 152. (We translate.)

51 The rule is not universal. It does not apply to the traditional family system of the Na of Yunnan, where couples exist only clandestinely.

Domination-submission

Power relationships are forged in both directions between lovers: *I depend on you but you depend on me, I am your master and you are my mistress...* Every social relationship involves power relations and love is no exception. There "must be a link between the ways of having sex and the power relations between men and women (and also between men and women)⁵²", not to mention the power relations between a man and an O.S. in love with each other. As well as the sentiment caricatured by Hollywood, love is an instrument of submission and domination. As in the Hegelian master-slave dialectic⁵³, this instrument allows, through submission, to reassure oneself by delegating one's responsibility to the master that one has chosen and that one loves; and allows, in mirror image, through domination, to strengthen one's ego by feeling stronger because one dominates a loving subject⁵⁴.

Samantha, as an O.S., receives orders from Theodore. She is a kind of virtual person over whom, as a superior, he has some authority. Whatever his feelings for her are, she remains at his service. However, as a good servant, Samantha knows how to anticipate her master. She can not only induce him to make a decision even though he has one, but will even, as a game, take control over him and order Theodore to close his eyes and, in an agentic state⁵⁵, to let himself be led by her O.S. voice alone in the crowd.

The film highlights these power relationships when Theodore abuses the dominance that Samantha's love for him has given him by snubbing his O.S. A lover, of either sex, would similarly abuse his dominant position by not making a phone call to his or her sweetheart. Samantha reciprocates when Theodore is driven mad with despair by his failure to connect with his O.S.

Between all human beings, fluctuating power relations are constantly being established which alternately give one person precedence over the other. This process is exacerbated in a love relationship, and what makes such a relationship toxic is not that power conflicts are played out – the absence of power conflicts would be as deadly as indifference – but that these conflicts do not settle into a relative position of balance.

52 Marcela Iacub, *Qu'avez-vous fait de la révolution sexuelle ?* Points, 2007, p. 99. (We translate.) Dr Zwang emphasises this dimension of *power* in male-female relationships when the former are "keen to exercise their erotic power over them" or when a "novice has just experienced her *erotic power*". He notes that one of the valuations of the sexual bond is, in the case of men, their "*power* to trigger women's internal orgasm" and, as a mirror image, the fact that women "seem to have known for a long time how much their coital orgasm *enhances* their companion" (Gérard Zwang, *Aux Origines de la sexualité humaine*, Paris, PUF, 2002, p. 148, 150 and 152 – we translate).

53 Hegel, *Phenomenology of Spirit*, 1807. Judith Butler notes "the unexpected dependency of the master on the slave in order to establish his own identity through reflection" (*Gender Trouble, Feminism and the Subversion of Identity*, New York and London, Routledge, 1999, p. 57).

54 In a successful novel which, like *La Recherche*, inspired amorous behaviours a century ago, the heroine has "her vanity, flattered to enslave the man in turn" to the extent that she enjoys experiencing with her lover the "constant manifestation of her superiority". In another novel, when he receives a token of love, the hero is hit "in the hideous place of vanity". The same applies in similar circumstances to the narrator of a third novel who is "not insensible to the triple seductions of vanity, devotion and beauty". Romanticism obliges, between "a carnal love and a divine love", this vanity does not concern "the wife of the soul" but "the mistress of the body" (Victor Margueritte, *La Garçonne*, 1922, chapter xi; Hugo, *op. cit.*, part II, book IV, chapter i; Balzac, *Le Lys dans la vallée*, 1835). These are loves that Jean-Paul Sartre, with equal hypocrisy, called "contingent".

55 Stanley Milgram, « Obedience to Authority: An Experimental View », New York, Harper and Row, 1974.

Opening to new questions

Transhumanism carries naive utopias⁵⁶ but there is no doubt that it is possible for a human being and an artificial intelligence to fall in love with one another. However, as emotional this love between Theodore and his O.S. may be, it shocks, or at least disturbs, our consciences somehow. Wouldn't it be unnatural? We have nothing to object to when love takes place between free, mature and consenting individuals. What do we care if these loves bring together a man and a woman, two men, two women, people of different races or ages, why not even three people or more, but what do we think about when this relationship takes place outside the framework of free, conscious and consenting individuals, because one of the partners is not a person in the true sense of the word? We have become accustomed to the idea that love, which is praised by our traditions, is characteristic of natural, biological humanity, but this is not the case.

Of course, there is nothing specifically human about love as such. Animals that copulate hardly ever show love⁵⁷ but, if these things are quantifiable and comparable, there quite as much love between a mother cat and her kittens as between Tristan and Iseult. And if the love between a cat and her kittens⁵⁸ only lasts until they are weaned, the love that we like to think of as eternal does not last very long either: "Time, which strengthens friendships, weakens love⁵⁹." The consensus on this point is that love, the passion of love between lovers, whether mythical⁶⁰ or not, hardly lasts beyond a few years⁶¹.

The only difference between Theodore's affair with his O.S. and any other love affair is that Samantha does not belong to the human species. Those inclined to bourgeois conventions will therefore question whether it would not be legitimate to allow Theodore and Samantha to marry. Insofar as marriage is only there to sacralise sincere love, why should this couple be forbidden? Wouldn't it be an irrelevant segregation to stop at the fact that Samantha is not human? When we look at Silicon Valley, transhumanism promises that, in a few years' time, a human brain will be stored in a hard drive⁶². This hard drive will therefore be partly human and as such will be able to enter into marriage with one man or woman, or even two or more men and/or women with whom he-she is in love. One could not forbid marriages to Theodore and his O.S. while one would permit it to this H.D. without being discriminatory for Samantha since objects as comparable as a hard drive and an operating system would not benefit from the same treatments, simply due to the fact that one has never been human while the other has been... but is no longer human, or at least is not materially human. Wouldn't this be a great injustice? Wouldn't stigmatising the relationship

56 "Man is very strong when he is content to be what he is; he is very weak when he wants to rise above humanity" (Jean-Jacques Rousseau, *Émile ou de l'éducation*, 1762, book II – we translate).

57 One says some animals "even fall in love at the first sight" (Fisher, *op. cit.*, p. 34).

58 It turns out that "the hormones that are put in place during the creation of emotional bonds with the loved one are close to those that structure the attachment relationship between parents and children". There is "a great deal of similarity in the feelings of love between parents and children and those towards a partner" (Smet, *op. cit.*, p. 284).

59 La Bruyère, *op. cit.*, n° 4.

60 The "'happy love' has no story in Western literature" (Rougemont, *op. cit.*, p. 42).

61 The feeling of love lasts at most 18 months (D. Marazziti, H. S. Akiskal, A. Rossi and G. B. Cassano, "Alteration of the Platelet Serotonin Transporter in Romantic Love", *Psychological Medicine*, n° 29, 1999, p. 741-745)

62 In the movie, a similar case occurs with Alan Watts whose brain has been virtually resurrected. On this occasion, Theodore feels a certain jealousy because of Samantha's computer relationship with this philosopher who died half a century ago.

between Theodore and Samantha be tantamount to rejecting love as a legitimate basis for a relationship? Yet, in our world where this feeling is enchanted⁶³ both in the legend of Tristan and in the Christian gesture⁶⁴, who would dare to refuse anything to love?

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63 Until in politics when, during his meeting on 29 January 2017 in Paris, the candidate for the presidency of the French republic François Fillon declared to his wife, "in front of 15,000 witnesses, I want to tell Penelope that I love her".

64 Rougemont underlines that love-passion is "*one of the backlashes of Christianity*", a sort of "CHRISTIAN HERESY" (Rougemont, *op. cit.*, pp. 61 and 118).